

RFC: Add New Dataspace Routines

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The HDF5 dataspace interface is missing features desired by users who want to do more with selections beyond what the HDF5 library currently provides. The current API does not provide an easy way to copy data from a user buffer described by a dataspace selection into another buffer with a different dataspace selection. Furthermore HDF5 does not provide an iteration routine for dataspace selections that is similar to the iterate routines for objects, datasets, and links. This RFC addresses those issues within the HDF5 API.

1 Introduction

An HDF5 dataspace defines the size and shape of dataset and attribute raw data¹. The dataspace API routines allow users to select a subset of a dataspace to read/write, instead of using the entire array described by the dataspace. Internally, the HDF5 library parses the dataspace selection and does what is necessary to perform I/O using that subset. Parsing the selection within a dataspace involves, for example, iterating over blocks of a hyperslab selection. This information tells the library where the data elements are located, whether on disk or in memory. Another internal operation on dataspace selections is to use, for example, a memory dataspace selection to gather data elements from a memory buffer to an intermediate buffer, where the data becomes contiguous and easier to perform I/O on. A scatter operation does the opposite - redistributing data elements from the contiguous buffer into a buffer accessed through a dataspace selection.

Right now the HDF5 library does not expose those internal routines to users, simply because there was never a need for them. Section 2 provides a motivation for exposing such routines. Section 3 describes the new requested API routines.

2 Motivation

HDF5 will be introducing the Virtual Object Layer (“VOL”), allowing users to write their own plugins to change the underlying storage for HDF5 data. Instead of accessing a local “.h5” file, VOL plugins give the user the freedom to select or implement different ways of storing the data.

As a motivating example for the routines proposed in this RFC, consider a client-server VOL plugin, where the data is stored on a remote machine in the current HDF5 native format. The client machine, where the user is executing the application, is responsible for forwarding HDF5 calls to the server machine that executes those calls. In case of a dataset write operation, it may be more efficient for

¹ http://www.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/doc/UG/UG_frame12Dataspaces.html

the client process to copy the data to be written into a contiguous memory buffer rather than transmit the entire memory buffer that could contain a lot of gaps or data that is not touched by the memory dataspace selection. An API routine that would enable such behavior is needed by the user to implement such functionality. Similarly, for a dataset read operation, an API routine that scatters the data from a contiguous buffer that has been read from disk, into a memory buffer using a memory dataspace selection is needed by this plugin.

The gather and scatter routines are performing a specific operation on a selection. A more general approach is to provide the freedom for the user to transfer the data to a new dataspace with a selection. The user would create a new dataspace, make a selection on that dataspace, allocate the buffer needed, and call a transfer operation that copies the data from the old buffer to the new buffer with the new dataspace selection for the data location. For a gather or scatter operation, the buffer provided would be a contiguous buffer of size equal to the size of the data needed and the dataspace would be a simple dataspace of rank 1 and an “all” selection.

HDF5 provides several types of iteration routines that allow users to provide a callback to be called when iterating over data elements of a dataset, file objects, and links. We propose to add an iterate routine, similar to the ones already defined in HDF5, to iterate over location sequences of a dataspace selection. The callback that the user provides would be called on every pair of coordinates and length that constitute the entire selection of the dataspace.

3 New Routines

3.1 H5Dtransfer:

```
herr_t H5Dtransfer(src_space_id, src_buf, type, dst_space_id,
dst_buf);
```

- hid_t src_space_id; IN: source dataspace ID with a selection
- const void *src_buf; IN: source buffer containing the actual data
- hid_t type; IN: datatype of the data to be transferred
- hid_t dst_space_id; IN: destination dataspace ID with a selection
- void *dst_buf; OUT: destination buffer where the data is copied into

Description: This routine will copy data from *src_buf*, where the data elements are of type *type*, and the location and length of the data that needs to be transferred are described by the selection in the dataspace *src_space_id*, into a *dst_buf* with the same element type, but in locations that are given in the selection of the dataspace *dst_space_id*.

3.2 H5Dgather

```
herr_t H5Dgather(src_space_id, src_buf, type, dst_buf_size, dst_buf,
op, op_data);
```

- hid_t src_space_id; IN: source dataspace ID with a selection
- void *src_buf; IN: source buffer containing the actual data

- `hid_t` type; IN: datatype of the data elements to be gathered
- `size_t dst_buf_size`; IN: maximum size of the data to be gathered before invoking the user callback
- `void *dst_buf`; OUT: destination buffer for the data to be gathered into
- `H5D_gather_func_t op`; IN: application callback to be invoked when `dst_buf` is full
- `void *op_data`; IN: pointer to application data that will be passed to the callback `op`

Description: This routine would gather [at most] `dst_buf_size` bytes from the source buffer, according to the selection in the source dataspace and [common] datatype, into the destination buffer, then call the application's `op_data` callback, giving the application a chance to "drain" the destination buffer and do something else with the gathered data. If more than `dst_buf_size` bytes worth of data are available in the source selection, `H5Dgather` repeatedly calls the application's callback routine. The prototype of the callback routine `H5D_gather_func_t op` is:

```
typedef herr_t (*H5D_gather_func_t)(const void *dst_buf, size_t
dst_buf_bytes_used, void *op_data);
```

where `dst_buf` is the buffer where the data is gathered, `dst_buf_bytes_used` is the size of the data in `dst_buf` and is always equal or less than `dst_buf_size` (specified in the gather routine), and `op_data` is the pointer to user data that is passed in to the gather routine. `dst_buf_bytes_used` will always be an integral multiple of the size of a datatype element.

The application callback will be invoked for each buffer of data gathered from the source selection, and the application should not depend on the contents of the destination buffer when this function returns. For example, if the destination buffer is large enough to hold 4 data elements, but the source selection contains 6 data elements, the callback will be invoked twice, once with the destination buffer containing 4 elements and once with the destination buffer containing 2 elements. Likewise, if the source selection contained only 3 elements (and the destination buffer contained enough room for 4), the callback would be invoked once, with the destination buffer containing those 3 elements.

3.3 H5Dscatter

```
herr_t H5Dscatter(op, op_data, type, dst_space_id, dst_buf);
```

- `H5D_scatter_func_t op`; IN: application callback to be invoked to retrieve data to be scattered
- `void *op_data`; IN: pointer to application data that will be passed down to the callback `op`
- `hid_t` type; IN: datatype of the data elements to be scattered
- `hid_t dst_space_id`; IN: destination space ID with selection
- `void *dst_buf`; OUT: destination buffer where data is scattered into

Description: Similar to the `H5Dgather` routine, the `H5Dscatter` routine calls the application's `op` callback to fill up a buffer with data elements, setting `*src_buf` to point at the buffer, and setting the number of bytes used in `*src_buf` in the `*src_buf_bytes_used` parameter, then scatters those values

into the destination buffer, according to the destination selection and the [common] datatype. Repeated calls to the application callback are made if the callback doesn't provide enough data to fill the destination selection. The prototype of the callback routine *H5D_scatter_func_t op* is

```
typedef herr_t (*H5D_scatter_func_t) (/ *OUT*/void **src_buf,
/*OUT*/size_t *src_buf_bytes_used, void *op_data);
```

where *src_buf* should be set to point at the data to be scattered, and *src_buf_bytes_used* will hold the size of *src_buf* in bytes, and *op_data* is the pointer to user data that is optionally passed in to the scatter routine. *src_buf_bytes_used* must always be an integral multiple of the size of a datatype element.

The application callback will be invoked for each buffer of data to scatter to the destination selection. For example, if the source buffer is large enough to hold 4 data elements, but the destination selection describes 6 data elements, the callback will be invoked twice, once to point at a source buffer containing 4 elements and once with the source buffer pointing at 2 elements. Likewise, if the destination selection contained only 3 elements (and the source buffer contained enough room for 4), the callback would be invoked once, to set the pointer to a source buffer containing those 3 elements.

3.4 H5Sselect_iterate

```
herr_t H5Sselect_iterate (dataspace_id, op, op_data);
```

- `hid_t dataspace_id;` IN: dataspace id with selection
- `H5S_select_iterator_t op;` IN: user defined callback
- `void *op_data;` IN: user data passed down to the callback op

Description: This routine will iterate over all sequences of a dataspace selection, and call a user defined function callback, *op* (defined next), on every sequence of elements selected. A sequence here is defined as a pair of coordinate (the location offset relative to the dataspace) and length (describing the contiguous portion in the dataspace selection starting at the coordinates) values. The *op_data* value will also be passed to each invocation of the callback routine.

The prototype of the callback function *op* is as follows:

```
herr_t (*H5S_select_iterate_t) (hsize_t *offset_coords, hsize_t
length, void * op_data);
```

where *offset_coords* is a pointer to an array of offset values for the sequence, and *length* is the number of elements in the sequence.

4 Recommendation

The proposed *H5Dtransfer*, *H5Dgather*, and *H5Dscatter* routines are necessary to complete in the short term, since they are required for progress on other projects, such as the client-server VOL plugin. Those routines are mostly implemented inside the library, and providing a public version with the proposed framework would not require a lot of work. We recommend implementing those routines as soon as possible, and wait for a more insisting demand from users to implement *H5Sselect_iterate*.

Revision History

July 31, 2012: Version 1 circulated for comments within The HDF Group.
August 21, 2012 Version 2 circulated for comments externally.
August 23, 2012 Version 3 circulated for comments within The HDF Group.
August 24, 2012 Version 4 circulated for comments externally.